

10, 10-Dimethyl hexacosan-7 one from *Euphorbia heterophylla* Linn.

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Euphorbia heterophylla Linn. (Euphorbiaceae) is an ornamental plant commonly known as Mexican-Fire Plant. It is widely distributed in tropical America, Texas, Western Himalayas and West Bengal¹. The present communication deals with the isolation of a new aliphatic ketone from petroleum ether extract of the leaves of *E. heterophylla*.

Study of 10, 10-dimethyl hexacosan-7 one :

The compound, C₂₈H₅₆O, m/e 390 (M⁺-H₂O), m.p. 76-77°, ν_{max}^{KBr} 2857, 2778, 1456, 730, 718 cm⁻¹ (aliphatic long chain), 1718 cm⁻¹ (carbonyl group)

and 2292, 1372, 928 cm⁻¹ (C-C type branching), ^{2, 3, 4}NMR (CDCl₃) δ 0.90 (s, 12H, 4C-CH₃ groups), δ 1.27 (s, 36H, 18-CH₂ groups), δ 1.78 (s, 4H, 2 CH₂ groups β to >C=O groups), δ 2.34 (s, 4H, 2CH₂ groups α to >C=O group), formed DNPH derivative, m. p. 90°, gave a hydroxy compound, C₂₈H₅₈O, m.p. 65-67°, ν_{max}^{KBr} 3226 cm⁻¹ (broad hump, hydroxyl group) on LiAlH₄ reduction indicating it to be a long chain aliphatic ketone.

The presence of 2 methylene groups adjacent to carbonyl group and 2 methylene groups β to >C=O group showed the absence of branching at α and β carbons with respect to <C=O group. Identification of *n*-hexanoic acid and *n*-heptanoic acid in the mixture of fatty acids obtained after KMnO₄ oxidation of the compound, indicates the straight chain nature of smaller alkyl group having 5 or 6 carbon atoms. The structure of the ketone has been elucidated by the study of mass fragmentation pattern of the ketone⁵⁻⁸ as shown in Table 1.

The mass spectrum does not show the molecular ion peak at m/e 408, instead a peak at m/e 390 (due to loss of H₂O molecule from the M⁺ ion) is observed. The other significant peaks appeared at 338

(f⁺, 26), 323 (c⁺, 30), 295 (d⁺, 55), 267 (e⁺, 55), 252 (h⁺, e⁺-CH₂, 40), 225 (g⁺, 23), 211 (i⁺, g⁺-CH₃, 42), 113 (b⁺, 76), 85 (a⁺, 100), 71 (a⁺-CH₃, 58), 57 (a⁺-2CH₃, 67), 43 (a⁺-3CH₃, 72), 29 (a⁺-4CH₃, 52).

TABLE-1

10, 10-Dimethyl hexacosan-7 one

Experimental

Isolation of 10, 10-Dimethyl-hexacosan-7-one :

The air dried, powdered leaves (3 kg) of *E. heterophylla* (supplied by M/s. United Chemical and Allied Products, Calcutta) were extracted with pet. ether in a soxhlet extractor. The extract was concentrated under reduced pressure and kept overnight whereupon a deposit (5 kg) was obtained. The deposit was separated dissolved in benzene and chromatographed over neutral alumina. Elutions with pet. ether yielded only waxy material while elutions with pet. ether : benzene (1 : 1 v/v) mixture yielded a solid (3.5 g) which was dissolved in hot pet. ether and left overnight at room temperature. The solid so obtained was separated by filtration and crystallised from CHCl₃ : MeOH mixture to yield 10, 10-dimethyl-hexacosan-7-one (3.1 g) as prisms, m.p. 76-77°, found C, 82.31, H, 13.80 per cent, calculated for C₂₈H₅₆O, C, 82.35 and H, 13.72 per cent.

LiAlH₄ reduction of 10, 10-dimethyl-hexacosan-7 one :

LiAlH₄ (200 mg) was added to a suspension of the compound (200 mg) in anhydrous THF (30 ml) in a flask equipped with a reflux condenser fitted with a CaCl₂-guard tube. The mixture was refluxed for 5-6 hrs and was allowed to stand overnight. The excess of LiAlH₄ was decomposed by the cautious addition of cold water. Working up in the usual way yielded a hydroxy compound, C₂₈H₅₈O, m.p. 65-67°.

KMnO₄ oxidation of 10,10-dimethyl-hexacosan-7 one :

The ketone (2.6 g) was dissolved in acetone (10 ml) and 5 ml each of 10% aqueous NaOH and 5% aqueous KMnO₄ solutions were added. The mixture was refluxed for 6 hrs. On working up in the usual

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way a mixture of fatty acids was obtained. The chromatographic examination of the mixture of fatty acids revealed the presence of *n*-hexanoic acid and *n*-heptanoic acid.

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